

Failure Modes and AE Characteristics of Carbon Fabric Composites

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ABSTRACT

Static tensile failure behaviors and AE (acoustic emission) characteristics of non-notched and hole-notched carbon fabric composites was discussed in the present paper .

Failure patterns of these composites were observed and then related to the AE parameters.

The experimental results show that the arrangements and locations of failures were dependent on weave structures . It was concluded that the initiation and propagation of different failure modes could be evaluated by AE parameters and the behaviors of micro-failure modes of notched specimens were affected by stress concentration and hole size .

KEYWORDS : Failure modes ; Carbon fabric composites ; AE method ; Fluorescent penetrant.

1. INTRODUCTION

Failure behaviors of FRP is very important and many researches have been carried out in the recent years with the help of various NDE methods . It is reported that AE method is effective to be used to track damage propagations in real-time in researches on failure behaviors of hybrid composites (1), (2) and CFRP (3), (4) . However , most of these researches are about unidirectional composites except a few on fabric composites (5) and (6) .

As a part of the research on relations of failure modes and weave structures of fabric composites, in the present paper two kinds of fabric composites reinforced by plain and twill weave carbon clothes are employed . Then , their static tensile failure behaviors are discussed by relating them to several AE parameters . Failures of loaded specimens are observed by using highly sensitive fluorescent penetrant and ultraviolet lamp , SEM and X-ray radiograph.

2. EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

Plain and twill weave carbon clothes are used as reinforcements in this study . They have 11x11 fiber bundles per square inch . Each fiber bundle is composed of about 6000 carbon filaments (toraca T300 , made by Toray co., Japan) .

In order to observe failures easily , only 1 ply reinforcement was used with epoxy resin in all the composites . They were fabricated by wet preprag method and after cured under the condition of 120 °C for one hours and a half . The mechanical properties of the employed materials are listed in Table 1 .

Table 1. Mechanical properties of materials

	V_f (%)	E_L (GPa)	G_{LT} (GPa)	ν	σ_B (MPa)
PC1	48.0	34.80	3.31	0.297	540.85
TC1	54.6	39.61	3.25	0.205	569.80

For notched specimen, center-holes of 3 mm or 8 mm in diameters was drilled by using diamond drills. The shape and dimension of specimens are shown in figure 1. Here, non-notched specimens with plain weave and twill weave reinforcement are named as PC1 and TC1, respectively. The names of hole-notched specimens, PCD3 and PCD8, mean that notched specimens reinforced by plain weave with a hole of 3 mm and 8 mm in diameter, respectively.

Figure 1. Shape and dimension of specimens

2.2 Experimental method

Specimens were tested in a universal Instron-type tensile machine with cross-head rate of 0.5 mm/min at room temperature. AE parameters were measured during the test with PAC Locan-at (Physical Acoustics Cooperation, U.S.A.). The pre-amplifier and main-amplifier are set in 20 dB and 40 dB, respectively. Threshold value is set in 30 dB. Here, 0 dB is defined when sensor's output voltage is 10 μ V.

A resonant-type AE sensor was employed. It was fixed in the center of non-notched specimens and above the hole at a distant of 25 mm for notched specimens. The resonant frequency of sensor is about 150 kHz.

Observations of surface failures were performed by using a microscope with the help of highly sensitive fluorescent penetrant for instant NDT (GLO-TEC HS-2) and long wave ultraviolet lamp for loaded specimens. For the observations of micro-failures inside specimens, X-ray radiographs and SEM were used.

3. Experimental Results and Discussions

3.1 Failure behavior and AE characteristics of PC1 specimen

3.1.1 Load-displacement curve and AE activities

Load (P) - displacement (δ) curve, AE total event count and total energy curves of PC1 specimen are shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. Load (P) - displacement (δ) curve, AE total event count and total energy curves of PC1 specimen

(1) P - δ , (2) AE total energy, and (3) AE total event count curves

From figure 2 , it is clear that after a short period of elastic stage , $P-\delta$ curve exhibits concave-type stiffness increasing behavior . Then , it gradually becomes to a straight line till final fracture .

It can be seen that AE activities begins at about 30% P_{max} . Then , the slope of AE total event count and total energy curves increases with load in low-loading stage . However , the slope of AE total energy curve becomes to decrease relatively to that of AE total event count curve from middle-loading stage to final fracture as indicated by K point at about 60% P_{max} . This means that after K point , AE signals of small energy become dominant indicating that there may exist failure mode change in different loading stage . It will be further discussed by consideration of AE amplitude distributions .

3.1.2 Failure process observed at several loading stages

Failure process are shown in figure 3 by surface failure patterns observed from loaded specimens at several loading stages .

Figure 3 (a) and (b) show that the number of cracks distributed on the transverse fiber bundle side of interlace regions increased from low-loading stage indicated by arrow A to middle-loading stage indicated by arrow B . According to the locations where these cracks occurred , this type of cracks is named as " transverse crack " . In high-loading stage , it can be seen from figure 3 (c) that the number of transverse cracks in each interlace regions had further increased and reached to about two per interlace region . Besides transverse cracks , however, white cloud-like patterns can also be observed on the border of all interlace regions . In figure 3 (c) , it looks like bold white wavy curves around the interlace regions .

After final fracture , it can be observed from figure 3 (d) that there also exists two types of cracks , Y-type and Arch-type cracks, as indicated by arrows . Figure 3 shows that these failure modes are deeply related to the weave structure . The explanations for the white cloud-like patterns , Y-type and Arch-type cracks will be presented in the next section after repeated observations .

Figure 3. Surface failure patterns of PC1 specimen
 (a) $P_A = 35\%P_{max}$, (b) $P_B = 55\%P_{max}$,
 (c) $P_C = 75\%P_{max}$ and (d) $P_D = P_{max}$

3.1.3 Failure modes and AE amplitude distribution

The following figures give some explanations for the white cloud-like patterns , Y-type cracks and Arch-type cracks first . Then , failure modes inside the specimen related to the AE amplitude distribution are discussed .

White cloud-like patterns are given in figure 4 . Figure 4 (a) shows that these patterns are composed of many short and white lines which concentrated on the borders of interlace regions. Clearly, they are crazings in the surface of resin rich regions . From the center of figure 4 (a) , it can be seen that crazings are also concentrated at two tips of each transverse crack and they formed a white Y-type patterns stretching to the longitudinal fiber bundle side of the neighbor interlace region . The schematic representation of crazings is given in figure 4 (b) .

Y-type cracks are presented in figure 5 . Figure 5 (a) is the surface photograph of Y-type cracks taken from fractured specimen and figure 5 (b) is the schematic representation of it . From figure 5 (b), it can be seen that Y-type cracks occurred at the tips of transverse crack in pairs in the surface resin . They are cracks in matrix and have angles of about $+45^\circ$ and -45° to transverse crack . Because this type of cracks occurs just before final fracture, it can be considered that it is the shear stresses applied to the surface resin which caused the Y-type matrix cracks .

Arch-type cracks are presented in figure 6 . From figure 6 (a) , it can be seen that besides

Figure 4. Mechanisms of failure patterns of crazing observed from PC1 specimen
(a) Photograph at $P = P_C$, and (b) the schematic representation of (a)

Figure 5. Mechanisms of Y-type cracks observed from PC1 specimen
(a) Photograph at $P = P_{max}$, and (b) the schematic representation of (a)

Figure 6. Mechanisms of Arch-type cracks observed from PC1 specimen
(a) Photograph at $P = P_{max}$, and (b) the schematic representation of (a)

some transverse cracks , there exists two pairs of Arch-type crack in the resin rich regions on the two borders of interlace region along longitudinal fiber bundles . They are matrix cracks in the form of Arch . Figure 6 (b) is the schematic representation of figure 6 (a) . It shows that some Arch-type matrix crack connected with Y-type matrix cracks .

Because the propagations of the two types of matrix cracks are determined by local stress distributions and slightly different patterns had been observed from glass fabric composites (7), it can be predicted that these patterns may be affected by the mechanical properties , geometrical parameters of weave structures and fiber volume fraction .

Comparing the above figures , it is easy to know that Y-type and Arch-type matrix cracks occurred in the crazing concentrated regions and so, they may be formed just before final fracture by the connections of crazings .

AE amplitude distribution of PC1 specimen is presented in figure 7 .

It is clear that AE signals can be divided obviously into two blocks , A_0 and B_0 , by about 75 dB line . AE signals in block A_0 begins in low-loading stage , and concentrates in the middle-loading stage . Then , their number decreases before reaching to P_{max} . However , AE signals in block B_0 begins in the middle-loading stage and their number becomes more and more till fracture . The different behaviors of AE amplitudes in the two blocks means that there are at least two failure modes , which becomes dominant failure mode in middle and last load-stage , respectively.

From the failure process shown in figure 3 and the AE amplitude distribution in figure 7 , it can be seen that transverse cracks are related to the AE signals in block A_0 . However , only from surface observations , a proper failure mode related to the AE signals in block B_0 couldn't found . This implies that another failure mode may exist inside the specimen .Therefore , attempts were repeated on searching failures inside specimens by observing edge surface .

Figure 7. AE amplitude distribution of PC1 specimen

The failure patterns on edge surface is shown in figure 8 . In low-loading stage at point A in figure 2, a transverse crack can be observed from figure 8 (a) which reached to warp inside the interlace region . Then , from middle-loading stage to fracture , a crack along the warp initiated at the tip of a transverse crack at point B and propagated at point D , as shown in figure 8 (b) and (c) , respectively . Because the crack is different from the definitions of debonding and delamination , so that it is called as " separation " representing the failure between warp and weft in one interlace region . Figure 8 (d) and (e) are the schematic representations of separation propagations shown in figure 8 (a) , (b) and (c) . It can be seen that separation is related to the AE signals in block B_0 as shown in figure 7 .

3.2 Failure behaviors and AE characteristics of PCD3 and PCD8 specimens

3.2.1 Failure process and AE Activities

Load (P) - displacement (δ) curve , AE total event count and total energy of PCD3 and PCD8

Figure 8. Microfractographs of the separation in interlace region of PC1 specimen
 (a) Transverse crack at $P_A = 35\% P_{max}$, (b) separation at $P_B = 55\% P_{max}$
 and (c) the propagation of separation at P_{max} .
 (d) and (e) the schematic representation of (a) - (c).

Figure 9.

Load (P) - displacement (δ) curve (1), AE total event count (3) and total energy curves (2) of PCD3 specimen ($P_E = 75\%P_{max}$ and $P_F = 95\%P_{max}$)

Figure 10.

Load (P) - displacement (δ) curve (1), AE total event count (3) and total energy curves (2) of PCD8 specimen ($P_G = 40\%P_{max}$ and $P_H = 75\%P_{max}$)

Figure 11. Failure patterns of PCD3 specimen

- (a) Transverse cracks shown by X-ray radiograph at $P_E = 75\%P_{max}$,
 (b) photograph of surface failure at $P_F = 95\%P_{max}$

are shown in figure 9 and figure 10, respectively. Surface failure patterns of these specimens are shown in figure 11 and figure 12, respectively.

Figure 9 shows that though AE activities of PCD3 specimen are similar to those of PC1 specimen in some extent, the K point (at about 75% P_{max}) on total energy curve is much near to final fractures. From figure 10, it can be seen that the slopes of AE total event count and total energy curves of PCD8 specimen increase in the same way till fracture. The difference of AE activities during PCD3, PCD8 notched specimens and PC1 specimen can be considered as the effect of stress concentration and the hole size.

Figure 12. Surface failure patterns of PCD8 specimen
 (a) Photograph at $P_G = 40\%P_{max}$, and (b) at $P_H = 75\%P_{max}$

Figure 11 shows that in the regions away from notch, surface failure patterns of PCD3 specimen, such as, transverse cracks, Y-type and Arch-type patterns just before final fracture are almost the same with those of PC1 specimen. Besides the above failures, in figure 11 (a) there are also two longitudinal cracks at the tips of the hole-notch which occur after transverse cracks as can be seen from figure 11 (b). Figure 12 shows that surface failures of PCD8 specimen exhibits almost the same behaviors with that of PCD3 specimen. It also can be seen that longitudinal cracks of PCD8 specimen occur after transverse cracks.

3.2.2 AE amplitude distributions

AE amplitude distribution of PCD3 and PCD8 specimens are presented in figure 13.

Figure 13 shows that though AE signals in block B₁ occurred just after those in A₁, AE signals in block B₂ occurred before those in A₂. Comparing figure 7 with figure 13, it is easy to see that the AE signals in B₂, B₁ and B₀ generated gradually earlier than those in A₂, A₁ and A₀, respectively. This seems to have little relations with longitudinal cracks because they occur after transverse cracks as can be seen from figure 11 and 12. This means that a failure mode related to the first stage of AE signals in block B₁ and B₂ of notched specimens exhibits a different behavior with those of non-notched specimens. In other words, the initiation and propagation of micro-failure modes inside notched specimens were affected by stress concentration and hole size.

Figure 13. AE amplitude distribution of PCD3 and PCD8 specimens
 (a) PCD3 specimen, (b) PCD8 specimen

3.3. Failure behavior and AE characteristics of TC1 , TCD3 and TCD8 specimens

3.3.2 Failure process and AE Activities

Load (P) - displacement (δ) curve , AE total event count and total energy curves of TC1 specimen are shown in figure 14 . Surface failure patterns observed at several loading stages are shown in figure 15 .

From figure 14 , it can be seen that the P - δ curve and AE activities of TC1 specimen exhibit almost the same behavior with those of PC1 specimen as shown in figure 2 .

It can be seen from figure 15 (a) that the number of transverse cracks in each interlace region reached about 2 at high-loading stage . Y-type cracks can also be observed after fracture from figure 15 (b) . Though these surface failure patterns of TC1 specimen are similar in some extent to those of PC1 specimen , their arrangements are obviously different from each other and dependent strongly on the plain and twill weave structures .

Figure 14. Load (P) - displacement (δ) curve (1), AE total event count (3) and total energy curves (2) of TC1 specimen ($P_I = 85\%P_{max}$, and $P_J = P_{max}$)

Figure 15. Surface failure patterns of TC1 specimen
(a) $P = P_I$, and (b) $P = P_J = P_{max}$

3.3.3 AE amplitude distributions

AE amplitude distributions of TC1, TCD3 and TCD8 specimens are presented in figure 16. From figure 16, it is clear that AE signals can be divided obviously into two blocks by about 75 dB line. From figure 16 (a) and figure 15, AE signals in block A₀ may related to the initiation and propagation of transverse cracks just the same as which discussed for PC1 specimen. Furthermore, it can be estimated from the distribution of AE signals in block B₀ that there is another failure mode inside the specimen. It may be the separation between warp and weft in one interlace region, similar to that of PC1 specimen.

Comparing figure 16 (b) and (c) with figure 13, it is obvious that AE behaviors of TCD3 and TCD8 specimens are similar to those of PCD3 and PCD8 specimens, respectively. This means that in notched twill weave composites, micro-failure modes inside specimens as separations may also be affected by stress concentrations and the hole size.

Figure 16. AE amplitude distributions of TC1, TCD3 and TCD8 specimens
(a) TC1, (b) TCD3 and (c) TCD8 specimens

4. CONCLUSIONS

From the results given above, it can be concluded as follows:

- (1) In static tensile tests, there are mainly two kinds of failure modes in carbon fabric composites reinforced by plain weave and twill weave clothes. They are transverse cracks and separations. Their arrangements are dependent on weave structures. Other failures of Y-type and Arch-type matrix cracks occur just before final fracture in the crazing concentrated regions.
- (2) Failure modes of transverse cracks and separations can be related to the AE parameters. It is also predicted by AE amplitude distributions for non-notched specimens that the transverse cracks and separations become dominant failure modes before and after middle-loading stage, respectively.
- (3) In notched specimens, it was found that AE activities and the behaviors of failure modes inside specimens were affected by stress concentrations and notch dimension.

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